

Responsible Privacy Heuristics - Experiment

This experiment is part of a Master's thesis titled "An Approach for Designing Responsible Privacy Heuristics". The experiment focuses on evaluating different versions of a privacy setting. The researcher will be observing the session to understand how the participant interacts with the interface of a privacy setting. The participant will read a scenario, change the setting according to the scenario and respond to a questionnaire. Please keep in mind that our main aim is to evaluate the design, not the participant.

The participant's activities are described below:

1. Read a scenario and let the researcher know when you are ready to start the experiment.
2. You will receive access to an application to complete the scenario-based task. The scenario text will remain visible in a split-screen view for reference.
3. Perform the task at your own pace. Let the researcher know when you finish.
4. Answer a short post-experiment questionnaire.

* Indicates required question

Data collection

We are committed to respecting your privacy. We will not collect any Personal Information such as your name, address, or email, and all information we collect will not be linked back to you. Here's what we will collect, how, and why:

- **Demographic and background information**
 - **What:** age, gender, occupation, education level, familiarity with social media;
 - **How:** the researcher will ask you and note this information in this document.
 - **Why:** to understand whether factors like age, gender and etc, might influence how people interact with the settings.
- **Screen recording**
 - **What:** a video of your screen while you perform the tasks (no audio);
 - **How:** we will use screen recording software during the task phase.
 - **Why:** to help us analyze how participants interact with the interface and notice details we might otherwise miss;
- **Questionnaire answers**
 - **What:** your answers to the questionnaires (the researcher may ask clarifying questions if needed);
 - **How:** you will answer directly in the document provided.
 - **Why:** to help us evaluate the designs and understand your experience.

1. Do you think using social media may negatively affect your privacy? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, I believe it affects my privacy
- No, I do not believe it affects my privacy

Demographic and Background Information**2. Age ***

 Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- 18-25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- over 45

3. Gender *

Mark only one oval.

- Woman
- Man
- Non-binary
- Other: _____

4. Occupation *

Mark only one oval.

- Full-time employed
- Part-time employed
- Student
- Homemaker
- Retired
- Unemployed

5. Education level *

 Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- No formal education
- Primary education
- Secondary education / High school
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree (PhD, EdD, etc.)

6. How long have you been using social media? *

Mark only one oval.

- I've never used social media
- Less than 2 years
- Between 2 to 5 years
- Between 5 to 10 years
- More than 10 years

Scenario: Reviewing Your Profile Visibility Settings

Imagine you've recently signed up for a new social media platform called *FriendlyApp*. This app allows you to create a profile, share and react to posts, connect with friends, tag others, and follow profiles that match your interests and activities.

So far, you've mostly been using FriendlyApp to stay in touch with friends. However, you're now planning to use your profile to connect with professional contacts as well.

Since creating your account, you haven't reviewed your privacy settings. With this new context in mind, you want to **make sure that the information visible** on your profile **reflects the image you're comfortable sharing**.

Please take a moment to **review and adjust** (if required) your **profile visibility settings** according to your current preferences.

You will see the following settings available for configuration:

- Who can see your profile description
- Who can see your birthday
- Who can see your email
- Who can see your friends list
- Who can see profiles you follow
- Who can see your tagged content
- Who can see your posts
- Choose if your activities show up in your friends' feed

Once you've finished reading this scenario, let the moderator know so the experiment can begin.

Questionnaire

7. **Choose the version as instructed by the moderator. ***

Mark only one oval.

Version A

Version B

8. How easy or difficult was it to use this interface? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1 - Very difficult
- 2 - Slightly difficult
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Somewhat easy
- 5 - Very easy

9. Were there any parts of the interface or information that made the decision difficult or confusing? *

Please describe.

10. How confident are you that the option you selected reflects your actual privacy preference? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1 - Not confident at all
- 2 - Slightly unsure
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Somewhat confident
- 5 - Confident

11. **Did you feel that the privacy settings interface offered enough information for you to confidently decide who should see your profile details?** *

If not, what was missing?

12. **To what extent did you feel pressured by the information in the privacy setting interface to choose or not choose a specific option?**

Mark only one oval.

- 1 – Very strongly pressured (I felt I had little to no freedom to choose anything else)
- 2 – Strongly pressured (The information or interface clearly pushed me toward / against a specific option)
- 3 – Moderately pressured (I felt some pressure that may have influenced my choice)
- 4 – Slightly pressured (I noticed a small amount of influence, but it didn't affect my decision)
- 5 – Not at all pressured (I felt completely free to make any choice without influence)

13. **To what extent did the information provided in the privacy settings interface help you understand the potential consequences of your choices (e.g., privacy risks)?**

Mark only one oval.

- 1 – Not at all (I didn't feel more informed about potential consequences)
- 2 – Slightly (I got a little bit of insight)
- 3 – Somewhat (I understood some of the possible consequences)
- 4 – Mostly (The information gave me a good understanding)
- 5 – Completely (I clearly understood the potential consequences of each choice)

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